

Plan for the dissemination and exploitation of results (including communication) - Initial

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Configuration Management

Nature of Deliverable		
R	Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)	X
DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.	
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs	
OTHER	Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.	
ETHICS	Deliverables related to ethics issues.	
DATA	Data sets, microdata, etc	
DMP	Data management plan	
Dissemination level		
PU	Public, fully open, e.g., web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS projects.)	X
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	

Disclaimer

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Glossary

Acronym/abbreviations	
ACS	American Chemical Society
CA	Consortium Agreement
CMOs	Contract Manufacturing Organizations
CDMOs	Contract Development And Manufacturing Organizations
DoA	Description of Action (technical annex to the Grant Agreement)
EU	European Union
GA	General Assembly
GAg	Grant Agreement (contractual document between EC and beneficiaries)
GhG	Greenhouse Gases
HTA	Health Technology Assessment
HCP	Health Care Providers
IHI JU	Innovative Health Medicine Joint Undertaking
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
LCA	Life Cycle Analysis
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisations
SSbD	Safe and Sustainable by Design
PDER	Plan for Dissemination and exploitation of results (including communication)
WP	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The aim of the Plan for the Dissemination and the Exploitation of the Results (PDER) is to provide the PHARMECO partners with guidelines on the different communication and dissemination activities that are planned and their schedule, who are the partners responsible for each activity and what tools and channels are available for dissemination.

More specifically, in terms of dissemination and communication, the PDER:

- Proposes a communication and dissemination policy, and defines the objectives of the actions;
- Identifies the target audience for each objective or main result;
- Lists the communication and dissemination channels to be used for project promotion;
- Presents a schedule of the communication and dissemination actions throughout the project duration;
- Defines and monitors a series of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to assess the success of the implementation

Specific details about the tools and means are included in the **Deliverable D9.1 - Project corporate identity, delivered in January 2025**, which is a public deliverable.

In this document is also provided a preliminary section on exploitation to introduce the actions planned to achieve the exploitation of the results and impact of the project. While this document mainly focuses on the communication aspects of the exploitation, further details regarding other aspects can be found in the related **Deliverable D9.10 - Exploitation and IPR plan – Initial**, also delivered in April 2025, but which content is restricted to the consortium.

In terms of exploitation of results, the PDER will contain the following information:

- The identification of exploitable main outputs of the project;
- The identification of the factors influencing exploitation and wide deployment of the project's results;
- The identification of new and existing measures for project sustainability.

The document is elaborated by Benkei, as leader of the task 9.1 - Visual identity, C&D strategic plan & activities, within **Work Package 9 - Dissemination, exploitation, communication and networking activities**, with inputs from all partners.

While Benkei is the leading partner in charge of the task 9.1, all partners have the responsibility to participate in the communication and outreach activities and dissemination of the project results. According to the Grant Agreement (GA) and unless it goes against their legitimate interests, each beneficiary must, as soon as possible, disseminate its results by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means (other than those resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including in scientific publications.

The PDER is an evolving document which will be updated at the end of its third year (M36 - October 2027), and at the end of the project (M72 – October 2030).

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1 Description of the deliverable's objective and the content

The **Plan for the Communication and Dissemination and Exploitation of Results (PDER)** summarizes the consortium's strategy and concrete actions to disseminate, exploit and protect the foreground generated by the PHARMECO project and will be used as a guideline to the Consortium for the dissemination and exploitation activities.

The two key areas addressed by this deliverable are the dissemination and the exploitation actions, which are separately reported in the Dissemination Plan and the Exploitation Plan respectively.

- Section 2.1 (Overview) reminds the objectives of PHARMECO as well as scope and objectives of PDER.
- Section 2.2 (Dissemination Plan including communication) describes the scheduled dissemination measures and activities. This deliverable aims at the presentation of a suitable dissemination plan for the project's promotion in Europe and beyond. Based on the plan described in the Description of Action (DoA), the main expected results, the key stakeholders' group, the dissemination tools and the preliminary target groups for dissemination in PHARMECO are identified and the subjects and matters of these actions are listed. The management as well as the tools and activities are defined and presented.
- Section 2.3 (Exploitation Plan) describes briefly the routes for the exploitation of results that project partners have envisioned at project onset. Elements are further described in the related **Deliverable D9.10 - Exploitation and IPR plan – Initial**.

2 Sections of the deliverables

2.1 Overview

2.1.1 PHARMECO in a nutshell

This short summary is to be used for any informal communication and does not need any further approval by the consortium.

The healthcare sector contributes 3-8% of CO₂ emissions in OECD countries and consumes vast resources. PHARMECO, supported by the EU and private partners of the Innovative Health Initiative, aims to transform the pharmaceutical industry by adopting more sustainable manufacturing practices. The project will explore innovative technologies and processes in chemical synthesis, biomanufacturing, and decontamination to reduce the use of solvents, substances of very high concern, energy, and water. It will scale-up Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) driven technologies, optimize manufacturing processes, and develop digital decision-support tools for sustainability steering. Additionally, PHARMECO will establish harmonized guidelines for environmental impact evaluation, providing a comprehensive toolkit for sustainable pharmaceutical production and life cycle assessment, ultimately fostering a greener and more responsible healthcare sector.

2.1.2 Scope and objectives of the PDER

The PDER is one of the main activities of **Work Package 9 - Dissemination, exploitation, communication and networking activities**, aiming to tackle activities that will maximize the impacts of the PHARMECO project.

The PDER is a living document, which implementation takes place along the whole project duration to ensure that the project results are taken up by the main stakeholder groups.

The PDER identifies:

- The stakeholders that will benefit from the work;
- The main messages to share with them;
- How those messages will reach them (the tools and activities);
- The process for managing the dissemination and related use of expected results for the project.

The Consortium attaches great importance to dissemination. All partners will contribute to that effort and will strive to maximize the use of all existing dissemination channels, such as high-quality papers containing the best scientific achievements and oral and poster contributions to national, international and European conferences. Industrial partners regularly participate in workshops, fairs and showcases where technical achievements and case studies can be presented to stakeholders.

The below scheme summarises the Communication and Dissemination activities targeted by the consortium, as claimed in the Grant Agreement (GAg).

Figure 1 Communication and dissemination planned activities and associated indicators

Table 1 Communication and Dissemination indicators

Communication
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Website > 3000 visits per year (18 000 visits over the project). Social media channels >2000 followers. 4 WP-based content webinars/year. >5 e-newsletters, factsheets, and digital brochures. 3 to 4 project press releases. 1 project video. 2 policy briefs.
Dissemination
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >20 overview presentations at different events. >50 scientific conferences and general conferences / symposia. >5 external interim events. 1 final event. >30 publications in scientific journals. >10 outreach articles. 1 final project booklet. >5 interactions between PHARMECO partners and other EU projects. 1000 open access Zenodo downloads

2.1.3 Open access and open science, Zenodo community

The PHARMECO project is highly relevant for European research and industry leadership. The consortium is fully committed to the Horizon Europe Open Access to Research Data scheme and overall open science policy. Thus, without compromising IPR (on the principle of being 'as open as possible, as closed as necessary'), the consortium will implement a general policy of open access and wide dissemination so that research findings are made available as soon as possible to all stakeholders including to the general public. As a general rule, the responsible partner undertaking open access will handle the main open science principles (among which curation and storing of data).

Further elements are also shared in the following deliverables:

- **Deliverable D9.1 - Project corporate identity**, released in January 2025.
- **Deliverable D1.12 - Data management plan (initial)**, delivered in parallel with this deliverable.

The PHARMECO website (www.pharmeco.eu) and the Zenodo community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/pharmeco-ihl/>) will enable to guarantee the free and long-term access to the elements shared publicly.

2.1.4 Difference between communication, dissemination, exploitation

It is important to clearly distinguish between communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities, as they serve different purposes within the project framework. To avoid potential confusion, the figure below outlines the key characteristics of each, highlighting their specific objectives, target audiences, and expected outcomes.

EUROPEAN UNION #HorizonEU

COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION & EXPLOITATION WHAT IS THE DIFFERENCE AND WHY THEY ALL MATTER

Communication

Inform, promote and communicate activities and results

For whom
Citizens, stakeholders and the media

How

- ✓ Having a well-designed strategy
- ✓ Conveying clear messages
- ✓ Using the right channels

When
From the start until the end of the action

Why

- ✓ Engage with stakeholders
- ✓ Attract the best experts
- ✓ Raise awareness of how public money is spent
- ✓ Show the success of European collaboration

It is a legal obligation!
Article 17 of Horizon Europe Grant Agreement

Dissemination

Make knowledge and results publicly available free-of-charge

For whom
For those who can learn and benefit from the results, such as: scientists, industry, public authorities, policymakers, civil society

How
Publishing results in:

- ✓ Scientific magazines
- ✓ Scientific and/or targeted conferences
- ✓ Databases

When

- ✓ Anytime, as soon as results become available
- ✓ Up to four years after the end of the project

Why

- ✓ Maximise the impact of the action
- ✓ Allow other researchers to go a step forward
- ✓ Contribute to the advancement of world class knowledge
- ✓ Make scientific results a common good

It is a legal obligation!
Article 17 of Horizon Europe Grant Agreement

Exploitation

Make concrete use of results for commercial, societal and political purposes

For whom
For those who can take the results forward or invest in them, such as: researchers, stakeholders, industry (also SMEs), public authorities, policymakers, civil society

How

- ✓ Creating roadmaps, prototypes, software
- ✓ Sharing knowledge, skills, data

When

- ✓ Towards the end of the action and beyond, as soon as exploitable results are available
- ✓ Up to four years after the end of the project

Why

- ✓ Lead to new legislation or recommendations
- ✓ For the benefit of innovation, the economy and society
- ✓ Help to tackle a problem and respond to an existing demand

It is a legal obligation!
Annex 5: Specific Rules and Article 16 of Horizon Europe Grant Agreement

HORIZON EUROPE

Figure 2: Difference between communication, dissemination and exploitation activities

(source: https://rea.ec.europa.eu/publications/communication-dissemination-exploitation-what-difference-and-why-they-all-matter_en)

The European Commission defines communication as taking strategic steps to promote actions and results to various audiences, including media and the public, and engaging in two-way exchanges. Dissemination is described as publicly sharing results through appropriate means, such as scientific publications, without protecting or exploiting them (European Commission, 2021).

The primary goal of **communication activities** is to promote the project to various audiences in a manner that is comprehensible to non-specialists. The measures and activities undertaken should ensure effective communication of the following points:

- Engage with society at large;
- Illustrate how EU funding addresses societal challenges;

- Plan strategically with appropriate messages, mediums, and methods. (EC, 2021)

Dissemination activities focus on sharing project knowledge to maximize the impact of EU-funded research. These activities should:

- Share results with those who can best utilize them;
- Extend the value of results beyond the original scope;
- Be integral to good research practice and the project plan. (EC, 2021)

2.2 Communication and dissemination plan

To support the scalability of PHARMECO and maximize its impact, a multi-level strategy will be implemented. This approach focuses on:

- ensuring that at the end of the project, the uptake of tools/methods/methodologies in relevant communities is assessed; and
- providing enough information and confidence to encourage further scientific and market exploitation.

2.2.1 Scientific Advisory Board

A PHARMECO Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) is being appointed to officially include strategic stakeholders representing a diverse range of fields across the entire value chain. The SAB will provide independent, expert guidance to ensure the scientific excellence, relevance, and innovation of the project.

The SAB members have been identified during the project proposal preparation or at project early stages. After an approval step by the General Assembly (GA) they will sign the Advisory Agreement, that is included as Appendix 12 to the PHARMECO Consortium Agreement and will participate to selected project activities.

2.2.2 Relevant target stakeholders for communication and dissemination activities

PHARMECO will make every effort to identify and actively engage as many relevant stakeholders as possible across key target groups and the global value chain, maximizing the project's impact.

Project objectives associated to key messages and relevant target groups are summarised in

Table 2.

Table 2 Key messages and target groups

Objectives	Messages	Target groups
➔ Facilitate the adoption of eco-friendly processes and motivate industry-wide change through shared data on reduced resource consumption and	Novel decision-making tools, accessible Safe and sustainable by design (SSbD) framework, features/benefits of innovative green chemical processes Innovative fermentation, cultivation, and purification	Pharmaceutical industry incl. Contract Manufacturing Organizations (CMOs) and Contract Development and Manufacturing organizations (CDMOs), Medical device industry; American Chemical Society (ACS)

Objectives	Messages	Target groups
Greenhouse Gases (GHG) emission	Novel sustainable decontamination processes for sustainability	Biotech and -manufacturing firms; NIIMBL Health technology assessment (HTA) offices, Health care providers (HCPs): Procurement; Chemicals, Consumables and Equipment Suppliers
→ Promote the use of novel tools and increase environmentally conscious practices + training	Share data, features and facts of innovative approaches for sustainable manufacturing and decontamination	Academic institutions and Research and Technical Organisations Financing bodies
→ Create a unified approach to sustainability assessment	Promote a shared understanding for sustainability	Healthcare stakeholders like PEF, DG-JRC, and EMA. Collaborative organizations (e.g., SMI, BSI, the ACS GCI Pharmaceutical Roundtable and Pharmaceutical Environment Group, Biophorum), environmental Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs)
→ Adoption of standardized frameworks for reliable LCA results	Ensure alignment of standardized frameworks	Pharmaceutical industry incl. supply chain actors, Life Cycle Analysis (LCA) practitioners (e.g., EPLCA)
→ Contribute to the development of policies that promote sustainable pharmaceutical manufacturing	Recommendations for shaping policies to establish the sustainability assessments as industry norms, integrating environmental guidelines into the industry's standard operating procedures.	Regulatory and policy-making bodies (e.g., ISO, UNEP, EMA, ECHA, EEA, EU Commission, EU Parliament ENVI Committee, National Drug Regulatory Agencies, national regulatory authorities)

Within project early stages, in the frame of Work Package 9, task 9.2 - Stakeholder engagement & networking activities the consortium refined a list of stakeholders covering different target groups, based on the partners network. This list will be maintained in a GDPR compliant mode, with the individual sending of a dedicated email as well as the PHARMECO privacy policy (templates reproduced in annex). The engagement of these stakeholders is further defined in **D9.5 - Stakeholder engagement activities – Initial**, delivered in parallel to this document.

The key messages, defined during the project proposal stage will be as well refined during the first months of the project.

PHARMECO will also engage in clustering activities with other consortia and relevant organisations, funded in other Horizon Europe or IHI JU calls. This will be facilitated since some partners are common to the consortia.

Table 3 List of projects identified for clustering / networking

Acronym (cordis link)	Title	Coordinator	Main PoC
<u>ETERNAL</u>	Boosting the reduction of the environmental impact of pharmaceutical products throughout their entire life cycle.	AIMPLAS - Asociacion De Investigacion De Materiales Plasticos Y Conexas (ES)	Pablo Ferrer Pérez
<u>SusPharma</u>	Merging sustainable and digital chemical technologies for the development of greener-by-design pharmaceuticals	Universita Degli Studi Di Bari Aldo Moro (IT)	Renzo Luisi
<u>TransPharm</u>	Transforming into a sustainable European pharmaceutical sector	Universiteit Gent	Christian Stevens
<u>Enviomed</u>	Understanding the lifecycle of pharmaceutical products to reduce the environmental footprint	RISA Sicherheitsanalysen GmbH	Stefanos Camarinopoulos
<u>ENKORE</u>	Circular, safe and sustainable packaging and single use device ecoDesigned solutions through healthcare environments	Medtronic	Yves Bayon
<u>Premier</u>	Prioritisation and risk evaluation of medicines in the environment	Radboud University	Ad Ragas

In particular, PHARMECO will define with those initiatives a collaboration scheme that sets up an information exchange methodology as well as dedicated events to share results.

2.2.3 Schedule of dissemination, communication, and outreach activities

The dissemination activities will be performed according to the following schedule:

- 1. **Initial awareness phase (first year):** PHARMECO project website set-up (www.pharmeco.eu), analysis of relevant information resources, identification of dissemination opportunities and creation of basic dissemination tools including graphical identity of the project (i.e. project logo, templates for project documents and for project presentations, fact sheets) – see **Deliverable D9.1 - Project corporate identity** for further information.
- 2. **Focused dissemination phase (Years 2 and 3):** the consortium will enrich the website, start publishing some results and participate in conferences etc. Preliminary project results will be presented to the target audiences, notably through the public deliverables (see section

Public deliverables). PDER release will be then updated before the project technical review assessment (at the latest M36).

- **3. Delivery phase (from fourth year):** The PHARMECO consortium partners will accelerate the delivery of project outputs. This phase will be focused on informing the target audience of the exploitable results. The final version of the PDER will be issued.

2.2.4 Dissemination management

2.2.4.1 Distribution of responsibilities

According to the Article 17.1 of the Grant Agreement:

“Unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, the beneficiaries must promote the action and its results by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public), in accordance with Annex 1 and in a strategic, coherent and effective manner.

Before engaging in a communication or dissemination activity expected to have a major media impact, the beneficiaries must inform the granting authority.”

Therefore, any opportunity must be embraced by individual partners or on collective basis through joint action by more than one partner. **All partners of the consortium must therefore contribute to the dissemination** according to their foreseen role and effort and using all available tools, thus for instance by participating and giving presentations at conferences, publishing papers, answering to contacts, networking and similar activities and will strive to maximize the existing dissemination channels for the purpose of PHARMECO project result adoption.

According to the PHARMECO Management Structure, each Work-package leader and co-leader, task leader and deliverables owner or contributor will be responsible for the technical follow-up of their specific work as well as for the communication of the results to the Dissemination, exploitation, communication and networking activities WP leader.

2.2.4.2 Dissemination monitoring and reporting

An xls-based communication and dissemination log is implemented and available to all consortium members (available in the PHARMECO SharePoint). It contains a set of 7 excel sheets aiming at collecting planned and past activities related to communication, dissemination and conference attendance, to anticipate timely GA approval of these activities and keep track of past activities to facilitate reporting.

Figure 3 Dissemination & Exploitation including Communication activities register various sheets

PUBLICATIONS																
Nb.	Partner	Type of PID (repository)	PID of deposited publication	PID (Publisher version of record)	Type of publication	Link to publication	Title of scientific publication	Authors	Title of the Journal or equivalent	Number	ISSN or eISSN	Publisher	Month of publication	Year of publication	Was the publication available in open access through the repository at the time of publication?	Peer-reviewed
1																
2																
3																
4																
5																
6																
7																
8																
9																
10																

Figure 4 Extract from the “PUBLICATIONS” sheet

For monitoring purposes, the dissemination activities will be reassessed regularly by the General Assembly (GA) and gathered in the successive PDER releases.

2.2.4.3 Dissemination policy and rules

The Grant Agreement (GA) article 17 and specific rules associated to IHI JU and Horizon Europe projects as well as the Consortium Agreement (CA) section 6.6 define specific dissemination policy and rules for PHARMECO, that have to be well-known and applied by any of the consortium members. It notably deals with Dissemination of own and joint results as well as early notification (when a paper is planned) and a reminder will be shared regularly among the consortium especially with newcomers. All consortium partners are requested to follow the processes outlined in the following flows:

Default approval process (as agreed in the consortium agreement): applies to more detailed scientific dissemination material, like scientific A1 papers, keynote lectures on conferences, white papers, policy briefs

Figure 5 Default dissemination activity approval process (D = date of the activity)

It is nevertheless acknowledged by the entire Consortium that it is not always possible to respect the 60 days prior notice and a short-track option is suggested (for lighter documents).

Short-track approval process: applies to high-level scientific dissemination material, like abstracts, poster, pitch.

Figure 6 Short track dissemination activity approval process (D = date of the activity)

However, it is reminded the Consortium Agreement rule prevails on this adapted flow, especially in case of objection.

For all flows, an objecting partner can request a publication delay from the time it raises such an objection. If needed, alterations and modification to the publication can be made. During this embargo, the submission is possible, but authors should be able to withdraw the paper in case of objection. After this embargo or if no partner objects within the period above, the dissemination is allowed. In case of dispute, the procedure for settlement of disputes as laid down in the Consortium Agreement applies.

The actions of identifying the potential communication and dissemination activities will be organized through the monthly Work Package meetings.

The partners shall also remind that nothing in the PHARMECO Consortium Agreement shall be construed as conferring rights to use in advertising, publicity or otherwise the name of the Beneficiaries or any of their logos or trademarks without their prior written approval.

2.2.5 Communication tools and associated plan

A dedicated deliverable, **D9.1 – Project corporate identity**, is presenting the various supports to be used within the project for communication purpose (not specific to any target groups). A list is reminded below:

- Project graphic identity (logo and branded charter);
- Project fact sheet (PHARMECO in a nutshell);
- Project presentation (public summary of objectives and expected results);
- Project poster;
- Project public website;
- Project LinkedIn Page;
- Project Zenodo community page.

2.2.6 Dissemination plan

2.2.6.1 Publication in Scientific and Technical journals, public deliverables release, conference proceedings and technical magazines

The partners will individually and in collaboration publish and present scientific advances in technical papers as well as in journals (peer reviewed or not) and magazines. Scientific publications and release of scientific public deliverables are an effective way to disseminate high-level project information and to attract the interest of representatives of the various target groups.

2.2.6.1.1 Targeted events and papers and conferences

Publications in specialized magazines, papers sent to related events will attract the attention of technicians and researchers as well as to give the opportunity to collaborate within the purposes of PHARMECO.

In order to support this activity, whenever possible, project publications will be stored on a PHARMECO Zenodo community site, enabling to enhance the visibility for all the activities, including public deliverables.

The table below shows events, journals and magazines – both targeting scientific and industry impact - that are especially relevant for the communication strategy of the project.

Table 4 Communication & dissemination tools and proposed dissemination activities

Means	Targets
Peer-reviewed scientific papers	Sustainable Chemistry and Pharmacy Chemistry Today / SpecChem J. Chem. Info. Model. / J. Cheminformatics Angewandte Chemie Chemical Science Chromatography journals Organic Process Research and Development Journal of the American Chemical Society Current Research in Toxicology
Scientific conferences	International Symposium on Biocatalysis & Biotransformations Gordon Conference on Biocatalysis BioCat conference Flow Chemistry Europe conference Organic Process Research and Development conference Annual Green Chemistry & Engineering Conference Tetrahedron Symposium Continuous Flow Reactor Technology for Industrial Applications International Conference on Microreaction Technology International Oligonucleotides and Peptides Conference

Means	Targets
Scientific conferences	Pharmaceuticals, Biopharmaceutics and Pharmaceutical Technology world meeting European Peptide Symposium / Synthesis Conference AIChE / CRS Annual Meetings APV Continuous Manufacturing Conference Life Cycle Management Conference Ecobalance Conference Process Chemistry Symposium EuroTOX Society of Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry Biopharma Sustainability Roundtable Biopharma Networking Event BioProcess International Europe Bioprocessing Summit Europe ISPE Facilities of the Future Centre of Excellence in Sustainable Pharmaceutical Engineering and Manufacturing Conference
Networks, associations, NGOs	European Medicines Agency Innovation Task Force (ITF) United Nations Environment Programme European Environmental Bureau (EEB) EFPIA & EFPIA Working Groups (Climate, CEEN, etc.) National Institute for Innovation in Manufacturing Biopharmaceuticals (NIMBL) American Chemical Society - Green Chemistry Institute Pharmaceutical Roundtable Pharma LCA Consortium, Pharmaceutical Environmental Group (PEG), Sustainable Healthcare Coalition (SHC) Forum for Sustainable Life Cycle Innovation (FSLCI) BioPhorum Sustainable Markets Initiative (SMI)

2.2.6.1.2 Public deliverables

The consortium has planned to deliver 36 public deliverables, among which 28 are science related. They will be available for download on a Zenodo community, enabling to monitor the number of downloads.

Table 5 List of public deliverables (they will be published on Cordis and on Zenodo)

N°	Title	Del date*
D1.12	Data management plan (initial)	30/04/25
D1.13	Data management plan update 1	31/10/27
D1.14	Data management plan update 2	31/10/30
D2.2	Proposal for improvement common practice/ methodology for small molecules route design	30/04/26
D2.7	Proposal for improvement common practices/methodology for large molecules route design	30/04/26
D3.4	Chemically intensified photo-flow processes	30/04/29
D3.5	Chemically intensified electrochemical synthesis	30/04/29
D4.1	Intensified biomanufacturing system for Rec Prn including PAT Strategy developed	31/10/26
D4.4	Process data from demonstration run	31/10/27
D4.5	Model-based advanced process control (APC)	31/10/27
D4.9	Utilization breakdown	31/10/30
D4.11	Evaluation of Renewable/Recyclable single-use materials	31/10/30
D5.4	New wastewater remediation method optimized in lab scale	31/10/27
D7.1	PharmECO tools and concepts in accordance with an SSbD approach for the pharmaceutical sector	31/10/30
D7.6	Prospective environmental sustainability assessment of full scale innovative pharmaceutical technologies	31/10/30
D7.7	Concept of an end-to-end integrated sustainability evaluation scheme for pharmaceuticals	31/10/27
D7.9	Specifications for a public digital decision support for facilitating operationalization in industry	29/02/28
D7.11	Digital decision support tool to pharmaceutical production	31/10/30
D8.1	Scoping Document	31/10/25
D8.2	Methodology Paper	31/10/27
D8.3	Draft Guideline	30/04/28
D8.4	Road-Testing Report	31/10/29
D8.5	Final Guideline	31/10/30
D9.1	Project corporate identity	31/01/25
D9.2	Plan for the dissemination and exploitation of results (including communication) – Initial	30/04/25
D9.3	Plan for the dissemination and exploitation of results (including communication) - Update	31/10/27
D9.4	Plan for the dissemination and exploitation of results (including communication) - Final	31/10/30
D9.5	Stakeholder engagement activities - Initial	30/04/25
D9.6	Stakeholder engagement activities - Update 1	30/04/26
D9.7	Stakeholder engagement activities - Update 2	31/10/27
D9.8	Stakeholder engagement activities - Update 3	30/04/29
D9.9	Stakeholder engagement activities - Final	31/10/30
D9.13	Inventory of key issues	31/10/25
D9.14	Set of policy briefs and their public summaries - V1	31/10/27
D9.15	Set of policy briefs and their public summaries - V2	31/10/29
D9.16	Public seminar	31/10/30

* from Annex 1 to the GAg (as of the date of preparation of this report).

2.2.7 Key performance indicators

For the purposes of evaluation of PHARMECO dissemination activities and impact, quantitative indicators and associated metrics are proposed. A numerical target (KPI) has been estimated as a cumulative estimate based on individual partners' inputs. These targets will be periodically reviewed by the WP9 and tasks leaders in collaboration with the Steering Team (assembly of Work Package leaders and co-leaders).

Table 6 Indicators and associated metrics for evaluation of the dissemination activities

Communication mean	Indicator	Objective	Contingency plan
Website	Number of total users	18 000	Promoting the web site in Social Networks and newsletter / emailing to target groups
	Number of pages views	45 000	Publish regularly news and communicate on updates
	Number of references from external pages (google occurrence)	100	Contact more stakeholders and initiatives to agree on the promotion of the site
Video media	Youtube: Number of followers	2000	1 project general video Interviews to be organised at each General Assembly meeting
Social media	LinkedIn: Number of Followers	2000	Definition of a Social media communication plan. Monthly report of Social Media activity and engagement to analyse performances and plan future strategies.
Publications	Peer-reviewed articles	30	Submit peer review papers to conferences partners are participating regularly
	Outreach articles	10	Establish a list of journals during Year 2.
	Press releases/factsheets	4	1 per reporting period
	Newsletter	5	Editorial content to be defined 6 months in advance
	Final booklet	1	Elaborate the ToC from Year 3, identify chapters owners
	Policy briefs	2	Establish a list of subjects possibly interesting for policy briefs during Year 2
Events attendance	Conferences	50	Ask partners the list of possible conferences during WPs monthly meetings (starting from Year 2)
	Networking events	5	Organise a planning with the selected European Projects
Events organization	Webinars	24	List at least 2 topics per scientific WP in project early stages

Communication mean	Indicator	Objective	Contingency plan
	Final event	1	Will be associated to one major event /conference
Documents sharing	Downloading of public documents (Zenodo)	1000	Higher visibility on the website and frequent reminder on LinkedIn

2.3 Exploitation strategy

The exploitation activities will be coordinated by the Exploitation Manager (EM), from UCB BE, who will work in close collaboration with WP9 leader and co-leader and the consortium.

The potential outcomes of PHARMECO are very relevant and strategic for all the industrial partners involved in the Consortium. For this reason, the General Assembly will ensure to consider the strategic viewpoints of both the industrial and academic partners.

Two types of results can be distinguished:

- **General results, conceptual frameworks, specific knowledge, etc.** Those results might not be commercially sensitive, unless specific industry elements are included. Most of the results of the PHARMECO project shall fall under this category, as the PHARMECO project default category. These results will be made publicly accessible (via deliverables and/or articles and/or presentations) during the course of the project. These results will remain confidential until published by the party(ies) that has(ve) worked on the results, and will not be published or otherwise disseminated by any other parties unless there is explicit approval from the party(ies) that has(ve) generated such results, and following the approval flows described in 2.2.4.3.
- **Commercially sensitive results**, e.g., to be protected (patent or secret). These are the exception to the above category, and will not be made publicly available, or only after the end of the embargo in the case of patent.

As to be detailed in **Deliverable D9.10 - Exploitation and IPR plan - Initial**, the consortium will follow an internal process composed of the following tasks:

2.3.1 Intellectual Property Rights Management

Partners will take care, with the IP departments, of protecting their intellectual property developed during the project from possible external threats. Discussions will be organized on plans and activities performed, during each General Assembly meeting. An awareness training will be proposed by UCB BE to the early stage researchers if not covered by their organizations.

2.3.2 Exploitable Results Identification

As soon as possible, the consortium will update the Key Exploitable Results (KER) mapping (Annex I Deliverable D9.10 - initial Exploitation and IPR plan) listing the potential results that could be exploited. This mapping will ideally be done during dedicated sessions including all members of the consortium. Exploitation Strategy Seminars offered by external consultants (Horizon Booster) might as well be considered.

2.3.3 Market Analysis and Business Model

The consortium will work, based on the list of KERs, on a market analysis to assess the potential of each result. It encompasses a quantitative and qualitative assessment looking into the size of the market both in volume and in value, the various customer segments and buying patterns, the competition, and the economic environment in terms of entry barriers and regulation.

To design the business model for a specific result, the consortium will use frameworks such as the Business Model Canvas and the Value Proposition Canvas. It will enable to have a preliminary roadmap with target users, the potential sales strategies (direct sales, licensing, joint venture, spin out...), requirements for further technology development/scale-up to support market entry etc.

3 Conclusion

The deliverable presents both the plans targeted by the consortium to efficiently implement, manage and monitor the Dissemination (and Communication) and Exploitation activities.

It is and will be completed with the following deliverables released all along the project progress, namely (ranked on a time scale basis):

Table 7 Upcoming deliverables related to dissemination and exploitation activities (including communication)

Del	Title	Owner	Diss Level	Project Month release	Date release
D9.1	Project corporate identity	Benkei	PU	3	31/01/25
D9.10	Exploitation and IPR plan - Initial	UCB BE	SEN	6	30/04/25
D9.3	Plan for the dissemination and exploitation of results (including communication) - Update	Benkei	PU	36	31/10/27
D9.11	Exploitation and IPR plan - Update	UCB BE	SEN	36	31/10/27
D9.4	Plan for the dissemination and exploitation of results (including communication) - Final	Benkei	PU	72	31/10/30
D9.12	Exploitation and IPR plan - Final	UCB BE	SEN	72	31/10/30